

Marketing Mix for Tourism in the Chonburi Province

Pisit Potjanajaruwit

Abstract—The objectives of the study were to determine the marketing mix factors that influencing tourist's destination decision making for cultural tourism in the Chonburi province. Both quantitative and qualitative data were applied in this study. The samples of 400 cases for quantitative analysis were tourists (both Thai and foreign) who were interested in cultural tourism in the Chonburi province, and traveled to cultural sites in Chonburi and 14 representatives from provincial tourism committee of Chonburi and local tourism experts. Statistics utilized in this research included frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and multiple regression analysis. The study found that Thai and foreign tourists are influenced by different important marketing mix factors. The important factors for Thai respondents were physical evidence, price, people, and place at high importance level. For foreign respondents, physical evidence, price, people, and process were high importance level, whereas, product, place and promotion were moderate importance level.

Keywords—Chonburi Province, Decision Making for cultural tourism, Marketing Mixed.

I. INTRODUCTION

NOWADAYS for the past decade, cultural resources and tourism have become inextricably linked throughout the world especially in developing countries. The decision to pursue cultural tourism of the government agenda of many tourism destination especially those with colorful traditions and enriched cultural and heritage resources. [1]

Thailand has diversity in tourism resources; especially in geography, climates, biology and flora & fauna. These enable an increasing number of both Thai and international tourists to be able to choose to travel to many provinces of Thailand. Moreover, Thailand is also reputed in cultural tourism. In ranking cultural and traditional tourism in Asia Pacific countries, Thailand ranks number one in the region. However, to promote tourism products to attract tourists, many factors have to be considered such as understanding tourist preferences, quality of tourism products, standard services, suitable prices and effective advertisements. An effective marketing is needed in order to obtain guidelines in a tourist area management. Marketing management has to be carried out in line with a sustainable tourism management in order to generate a good income for the country and to help with the conservation for the contributions to a sustainable utilization of tourism resources.

Tourism Authority of Thailand has long been the core organization that raises the promotion of tourism in the country. Tourism Authority of Thailand (1997a: 7) claimed

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that the government has set up aims of tourism that the growth rate of tourist is to be at least 7 percent per year, foreign currency income at least 15 percent per year. And they tried to encourage Thai people to increase domestic tourism at least 3 percent per year [2].

Tourism Authority of Thailand compliance with the government prospect set up a 6-year plan since 1998-2003. It came with campaign of "Rak Thai Teaw Thai". The goal is to develop Thailand tourism in such a way that conserves cultural, social and natural heritage and enable sustainability of environment.

The government realized the importance of tourism to the country, thus promotes tourism in Thailand by adding tourism in some of the National Economic and Social Development Plans. And according to tourism policy of the Royal Thai government, under the responsibility of The Ministry of Tourism and Sports, there is an attempt to develop tourism industry to be "Tourism Capital of Asia" based on sustainable tourism promotions, and improve the tourism quality of Thailand to meet an international standard [2].

Because they realize that tourism is a very large scale business of trade and service that has been uninterruptedly developed and involves almost all production sectors at all level: local, provincial and national, so that it is regarded as a tool to develop an economy, society, quality of life and to conserve cultural, social and environmental heritage. In order to get more income from tourists, the seminar on "Tourism capital of Asia Goal" was held on 21 March 2003 which leads to be the quality of Tourism resource for more qualified tourists by emphasizing on the quality of tourism products to increase the value-added with higher personal income. The seminar has suggested one of the problems that stop the growth and development of tourism is a lack of marketing management. Despite good potential in unique cultural tourism resources, particularly tourist attractions, activities, local cultural festivals and local way of life, cultural tourism in Southern part of Thailand is not so well known like in The Northern and Central part of Thailand. So Thailand is not fully represented by short tours of Bangkok and Chiangmai [3].

This research studies methodology, guidelines in marketing strategies to bring about a sustainable cultural tourism by responding to tourist preference factors. Chonburi is selected for a case study for an implementation of a guidelines study.

Chonburi province is a potential province for cultural tourism but it lacks of a concrete marketing plan for cultural tourism. According to A study for national action plan for the tourism industry in the 9th National Economic and Social Development Plans (2002-2006), the analysis for identifying a

suitable province tourism development. It is found that Chonburi province is the potential province that needs more aggressive marketing strategies. Hence, it is suitable for a case study for this research [2].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concepts and Theories Relevant to Tourism

Tourism Authority of Thailand has defined tourism as a trip not only for pleasure and entertainment, as perceived in general, but also for studying, sport and recreation, business and family relatives visit [3].

The United Nations organized a conference on international travel and tourism in Rome, Italy and adopted in 1968 by the International Union of Official Travel Organizations (later to become the World Tourism Organization). The meeting agreed to have common definition of tourism because it had broad meaning. There was an agreement for members to replace the term 'International tourist' by 'visitor'. Visitor means as any person traveling to a country, other than that in which he or she normally resides, for any reason other than following an occupation remunerated from within the country visited. This definition was created for international travelers, but it can easily be adapted for tourists traveling within their own country (domestic tourist) by substituting the word region or area for country. Visitor thus can refer to 2 sorts of traveler.

Mill and Morrison said that tourism was difficult to explain, and difficult to consider it as an industry. Tourism itself was not industry, yet it enabled many kinds of related business. Tourism is an activity relevant to someone's traveling [3].

They also added that was no certain definition of tourism was applicable in general. There were some vague relations among tourism, traveling, recreation, and leisure. These relations were confusing. Nevertheless, to define tourism as industry under clear conditions, the clearer view of tourism could be seen by insider and outsider of tourism. In conclusion, tourism means temporarily traveling from the residence or domicile to another places willingly for leisure or pleasure of tourism activities or any purposes except earning or making living [4].

B. Tourist Attractions and Activities

Attractions and activities must be available to induce tourists to visit the area. Attractions can be natural such as nature parks and beach/marine areas, archaeological sites and historic places, cultural features such as arts and entertainment, crafts, traditional architectural styles, economic activities, traditional customs and ceremonies and 'man-made' feature such as theme parks and casinos and special events such as fairs, festivals and sports competitions. Many types of features can be developed as tourist attractions.

Thailand has tourism resources that are mostly concerned with base of folk styles such as natural resource, history, tradition and culture. From the past to the present, Thai tourism management were divided from that are natural

tourism and cultural tourism (include history and Archaeology)

After that the way that requested tourism to consider increasable conservation or cultural community reservation need had begun. So tourisms in present time are divided in 4 types:

- 1) Tourism in natural source is the tourism for relaxation, amusement and pleased about natural tourism. All of these are main objectives of this tourism. This tourism is the natural tourism.
- 2) Tourism that emphasizes on cultural, historical, archaeological appearance and many places that were built by humans. Moreover, it concern with social livelihood and it give knowledge to the foreigner. Consequently, it brings bride to the native.
- 3) Deliration and satisfaction on relaxation, amusement and entertainment of tourists, they emphasize appropriate services. This tourism is sport and entertainment tourism.
- 4) Tourism that there are objectives for convention and business. They may have observation and visual education. This is business and convention tourism.

1. Accommodation

Hotels and other types of facilities where tourists can stay overnight must be provided. Accommodation also often contains restaurants and other tourist facilities.

2. Other Tourist Facilities and Services

Tour and travel services are necessary to make travel arrangements for tourists and provide guide services. And other tourist facilities and services include restaurants and other types of eating and drinking establishments, postal facilities and services, medical facilities and services, banking and money exchange, retail shops, souvenirs shops, personal services such as hair dressing, and other types. Providing adequate public safety in the tourism area is essential to protect the tourists from criminal or terrorist acts. Proper public health measures to prevent environmentally based diseases must also be maintained [5].

Transportation can be by air, land (road and rail) and water (ocean' lake' river).Transportation includes both facilities and services such as aircraft, train and bus capacities, routes and schedules and efficiency of the services provided.

Other infrastructure required to serve tourism and tourist facilities include hygienic water supply, adequate electric power, proper waste management (sewage and solid waste collection, treatment and disposal) and adequate telecommunications.

These include education and training of persons to work effectively in tourism (human resource development), marketing and promotion of the tourist destination and its attractions and facilities, standards and regulatory mechanisms for tourist facilities and services including land use and environmental controls and often financial mechanisms to encourage investment in tourism development.

Organizational structures for tourism are essential and include both government tourism agencies and boards and association of private tourism enterprises.

The term used to define the supply side of the tourism system is the tourism product. The tourism product comprises the tourist attractions and activities, accommodation and other tourist facilities and services and the infrastructure that serves the attractions, facilities and services. A key concept in developing a successful tourism sector in an area is to match the tourist markets and the tourism product determines in part the types of tourist markets that can be attracted, and the product must be in suitable form to meet the tourist markets' expectations. The tourism product, however, must not be developed to match the tourist markets to the extent that it creates local environmental or social problems. Matching the tourist markets and the tourism product must be carried within the framework of achieving sustainable and balanced tourism development that optimizes benefits to the community.

In conclusion, the research will emphatically analyze the potential of cultural attractions and activities, and review with the following supply factors in Chonburi to examine the supply factors in terms of potential and limitations for promoting and developing cultural tourism in [4].

- Accommodation
- Transportation
- Other tourist facilities and services
- Other infrastructures
- Institutional elements

C. Concepts and Theories Relevant to Cultural Tourism

1. Definition of Cultural Tourism

Tourism can be defined in various meanings. WTO (2000) gave the definition of cultural tourism as the lifeblood of tourism. People travel not just to relax and recreate but to satisfy their need for diversity and their curiosity on how other people live in environments different from their own. Other people's lifestyle are expressed through their religion; festival; costumes; cuisine; arts; and crafts; architecture; music and dance; folklore; and literature. These cultural manifestations differentiate one group of people from another. They make life colorful and interesting [5].

Thailand Institute of Scientific and Technological Research referred the tour that emphasizes to culture, history, archeology and other man-made places and the rural community life style. Moreover Kaewsuriya, R. gave more explanations that it is the place for studying the belief, the respect in the rite and for getting knowledge, understanding the social situation and culture, having conscience to preserve environment and culture by the rural community coordinating in arranging in tourism [4].

The special interest tourism for cultural motivations, such as art and history tours, visits to museums and galleries, historical site and monuments travel to attend performing art and other cultural events.

Cultural tourism refers to forms of tourism that highlight the cultural, heritage or artistic aspects of a destination or experiences and activities for the tourist. Office of National Tourism 'Fact Sheet No 10 Cultural Tourism' defined Cultural tourism as tourism that focuses on the culture of a destination - the lifestyle, heritage, arts, industries and leisure pursuits of the local population [4].

IUCN charter for Cultural Tourism that can be defined as that activity which enables people to experience the different ways of life of other people, thereby gaining at first hand an understanding of their customs, traditions, the physical environment, the intellectual ideas and those places of architectural, historic, archaeological or other cultural significance which remain from earlier times. Cultural tourism differs from recreational tourism in that it seeks to gain an understanding or appreciation of the nature of the place being visited and explained more about cultural tourism that may be defined as that movement which involves people in the exploration or the experience of the diverse ways of life of other people, reflecting all the social customs, religious traditions, or intellectual ideas of their cultural heritage [5].

The National center for cultural and recreation statistics of the Australian Bureau of statistics. Cultural tourism is an entertainment and educational experience that combines the arts with natural and social heritage and history.

D. Concepts and Theories Relevant to Tourist Market and Behavior

According to a part of research determines the factors influencing tourist both Thai and foreign to make a destination decision to select cultural tourism in southern provinces, it concern with concept of consumer behavior. Consumer buyer behavior refers to the buying behavior of final consumers individual and households who buy goods and service for personal consumption. The starting point is the marketing and other stimuli enter the consumer's "black box" and produce certain responses, which shown in marketers must figure out what is in the buyer's black box [5].

The consumer behavior and factors influencing consumer behavior, the consumption marketing stimuli consist of the four Ps: product, price, place and promotion. Other stimuli include major forces and events in buyer's environment: Economic, technological, political, and cultural. All these inputs enter the buyer's black box, where they are turned into a set of observable buyer responses: product choice, brand choice, dealer choice, purchase timing, and purchase amount. The marketer wants to understand how the stimuli are responses inside the consumer's black box, which has two parts. First, the buyer's characteristics influence how he or she perceives and reacts to the stimuli. Second, the buyer's decision process itself affects the buyer's behavior.

Consumer purchases are influenced strongly by cultural, social, personal, and psychological characteristics, as shown in for the most part, we cannot control such factors, but they must take them into account [5].

Cultural factors exert the broadest and deepest influence on consumer behavior. The marketer needs to understand the role played by the buyer's culture, subculture and social class. Culture is the most basic cause of a person's want and behavior is largely learned. Growing up in a society, a child learns basic values, perceptions, wants, and behaviors from the family and other important institutions. Every group or society has cultural influence on buying behavior may vary greatly from country to country. Failure to adjust to these differences can result in ineffective marketing or embarrassing mistakes. International marketers must understand the cultural in each international market and adapt their marketing strategies accordingly [4].

A consumer's behavior also is influenced by social factors, such as the consumer's small groups, family and social roles and status.

a. Reference Groups

Many small groups influence a person's behavior. Groups that have direct influence and to which a person belongs are called membership groups. In contrast, reference groups serve as direct (face-to-face) or indirect points of comparison or reference in forming a person's attitudes or behavior. Reference groups to which they do not belong often influence people.

b. Family

Family members can strongly influence buyer behavior. The family is the most important consumer buying organization in society, and it has been researched extensively. Marketers are interested in the roles and influence of the husband, wife, and children on the purchase of different products and services.

A person belongs to many groups-family, clubs, and organizations. The person's position in each group can be defined in terms of both role and status. A role consists of the activities people are expected to perform according to the persons around them. Each role carries a status reflecting the general esteem given to it by society. People often choose products that show their status in society [4].

III. METHODOLOGY

This study is survey research in order to study marketing strategies for sustainable cultural tourism in Chonburi. In case of primary data were compiled by questionnaire and face-to-face interview to evaluated potential of Chonburi in being a cultural tourist attraction, and questionnaire to evaluate the factors for both Thai and foreign tourists to make a decision to select southern province of Thailand as a cultural tourism destination. In case of secondary data and general conditions of areas were compiled by search in document and concerned research. After that, it was analyzed and evaluated to be way to develop cultural tourism in Chnoburi. It has research elaboration as follow [3].

Fig. 1 Research Conceptual Framework

IV. FINDINGS

A. Participant and Respondent Characteristics

The primary purpose of this questions are to examine the personal data of respondents for analyzing the relation with marketing mix factors that influence tourists' decisions to select cultural tourism in South of Thailand for the survey showed that female were the most of Thai sample size at 59% and male 41%. Age of Thai sample respondents mostly were 26–35 year at 30.2%, and secondly 16-25 year at 26.4%, and 36-45 year at 24.4%, and 46-55 year 15.6% respectively. Most of Thai sample respondents were Southern people at 39.2%, whereas Central people 37.7%, Northern people 9.4%, and Northeast people 6.6%, respectively [2].

The Marital status of Thai sample respondents, the result showed that single were the highest of Thai sample size 53.8% whereas married 42.0%, and divorced or widow only 4.2%. While Education level of the most of Thai sample respondents had education level in bachelor degree at 56.6%, whereas lower than bachelor degree 36.8%, master degree 5.2%, respectively. Moreover, the most of Thai sample respondents was employee/company officer at 33.0%, whereas government officer/state enterprise 20.8%, commercial personnel 17.9%, student 14.2%, respectively. And most of them had income per month 10,000 Baht or less than at 41.0%, while between 10,001- 25,000 Baht 36.2%, between 25,001-40,000 Baht 11.4%, respectively [3].

The most of Thai sample respondents had influenced to their decision making to travel by family/relative 48.1% whereas with friend 33%, alone 18.4%. The highest main transportation that Thai sample respondents prefer traveling by private car/rental car at 67.9%, while by public bus 15.1%, by tour bus 9.0%. The visitor for holiday/pleasure at 85.9%, secondly for visit friend/relation 7.5% and for business 3.3%. The study revealed that respondents were most interested in cultural tourism in the South at 87.7% whereas perhaps interested in cultural tourism in the South 11.8%, and not interested in cultural tourism in the South 0.5%, respectively. Furthermore, the highest of Thai sample respondents was interested in cultural tourism in Chonburi at 84.0% while perhaps interested in cultural tourism in the South 15.6%, and not interested in cultural tourism in the South 0.5%, respectively. In addition, cultural tourist attractions and activities do the traveler prefer the most when visiting to the south is historic site and building at 16 percent, whereas the next highest cultural tourist attractions and activities were

festival and special event, traditional food and drinks, religious site, museum, site associated with historic.[3]

However, there were some other groups, which prefer traveling in traditional performance 4.4 percent, and only 3.4 percent prefers traveling in local sport [4].

TABLE I
THE DESCRIPTIVE OF THE PARTICIPANT CHARACTERISTICS

Characteristics	Mean	Interpretation
1.1 Gender	3.64	Effective
1.2 Age	3.67	Effective
1.3 Marital status	3.59	Effective
1.4 Education level	3.65	Effective
1.5 Average monthly income at present	3.66	Effective
Overall Mean	3.64	Effective

From the study between gender of Thai sample respondents and interest of cultural tourism in the South found that male (88.5% of male respondents) interest in cultural tourism in the South more than female (87.2% of female respondents). And the proportion of female (12.8%) cultural tourism in the Chonburi more than male (11.5%). While the interest of cultural tourism in Chonburi found the similar result with cultural in the South that male has higher interest than female. And female have higher perhaps interest than male. In addition, the study found that only 1 female (0.8%) in cultural tourism in Chonburi [3].

TABLE II
THE PREDICTOR OF THE FACTOR THAT MOST SIGNIFICANT

Predictor	Beta Coefficient	t	Significance
Price	0.509	11.189	.000

B. The Importance of Marketing Mixed Factors that Influence Tourist' Decisions

The study decided to use the 7Ps of marketing mix by Booms and Bitner concept. It includes product, price, place, promotion, people, process, and physical evidence to be the factors for purposing of finding the important level that influence tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the South for setting marketing strategies from 212 Thai sample respondents [5].

The study of the Thai sample respondents shown that high important level of product factors that influence tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the South were the variety of cultural tourist attractions and activities, famous cultural attraction places, unique cultural tourist attractions and traditions, image of cultural tourist attractions and activities, and restaurant and food service (price, quality, variety). And moderate important level of product factors that influence tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the South were accommodation, adequacy of infrastructures, novelty of the destination, adequacy of support services, hospital, special events, and night life and entertainment [5].

The study of the Thai sample respondents shown that high important level of price factors that influence tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the South were reasonable price, and cost of trip (trip cost, on-site cost). In the consideration of important level of Thai sample

respondents, price factors was high important level (Mean = 3.88) that influence tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the Chonburi Province [3].

V. DISCUSSION

In consideration of tourism behavior, Thai and foreign tourists mostly have similar tourism behavior, except the foreign tourists prefer to use plane as a major transportation because of saving time. As Thai tourists prefer to use private car or car rental as a major transportation because most of them travel with their family. This transportation is convenient, save a travel cost, and is high flexible for traveling time. The difference type of transportation should be considered to develop to achieve the need of tourists that are ease of accessibility to tourist attractions more than half of Thai and foreign sample tourists were interested in cultural tourism in the south. Moreover Thai tourists were interested in cultural tourism in Chonburi more than foreign tourists because foreign tourists did not have enough information about this province [6].

And cultural tourists as a whole generally possess certain characteristics different to those of other mass tourism activities. Leask & Yeoman concluded the common characteristics of tourists visiting cultural heritage attractions that are a tourist that have higher income, higher spending power on vacation, more likely to shop, higher educated than the general public, higher proportion of female visitors, and in older age categories. [6]

Thai and foreign tourists have different important level of marketing mix factors (7Ps) to make decisions to select cultural tourism in southern provinces. The marketing strategies for Thai tourists should emphasize physical evidence, price, people, place, product, process, and promotion respectively. Whereas marketing strategies for foreign tourists should consider physical evidence, price, people, process, product, place, and promotion respectively. Moreover, the study showed the most important factor that influence to make decisions to select cultural tourism in southern provinces, is safety and security in both sample groups because safety is the second needs of human needs (from Maslow's theory "hierarchy of needs) [7].

VI. RECOMMENDATION AND FUTURE STUDIES

The safety and security, and cleanness/sanitation are the key factors for tourists to make a decision to travel which related to the study indicated that safety and security is the second highest important level that influences tourists' decisions on selecting cultural tourism in the South. So government and local authority should maintaining and developing safety precaution measure for tourists and their belonging, and assistance facilities for example have tourism police or security guards in tourist attractions, and promote the image of safety city. And cleanness/sanitation, and weather/season are at high important level. They should set up sanitation measure, increase summary, the marketing strategies for Thai tourists should emphasize physical

evidence, price, people, place, product, process, and promotion respectively. Whereas marketing strategies for foreign tourists should consider physical evidence, price, people, process, product, place, and promotion respectively. Moreover the development of marketing strategies for sustainable cultural tourism in Chonburi should do under regarding the potentiality level of the province in being a cultural tourist attraction, which has moderate potential level.

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